

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF A PEER-LED SMOKING CESSATION SUPPORT GROUP

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Background/Significance

- Cigarettes have high addiction potential
- Cigarettes have up to 8K chemicals, carcinogens
- 22.5% world population smokes (1B adults)
- 60% smokers who continue to middle age die from smoking-related disease
- Evidence-based (EB) programs combine pharmacological and/or behavioral interventions = 15.7-35% success rate

Lynwood, CA

- Located in Los Angeles county, borders cities of Paramount, South Gate, Compton, & the unincorporated community of Willowbrook
- 13% current smokers
- No smoking cessation programs
- Disproportionate # of deaths - smoking related disease

Purpose Statement

To develop, implement, and evaluate a peer-coach (PC) led smoking cessation support group (SCSG)

Review of Literature

Barriers to Quitting Smoking

- Addiction, stress management, lack of support, motivation, high prevalence smoking in disadvantaged communities

Evidence-Based Quit Strategies

- Medication, and/or behavioral support
- Combing strategies increased quitting by 70-100%
- Adding social support to other EB strategies increases probability of quitting smoking

Current Practices

- Cold turkey or self help (<10% success)
- 70% smokers go to primary care for help
- 1-800-No Butts
- Online help
- Referrals to local cessation experts

Peer Coaches

- Attrition – no financial incentive, limited community recognition, personal time constraints

Smokers

- Cite lack of information and confidence as reason for not attending smoking cessation quit programs
- Community assessment Lynwood 12/19: Residents cite lack of financial resources as reason for not focusing on health

PRECEDE-PROCEED Model

Methods

Peer Coach Recruitment	Peer Coach Training	Smoker Recruitment	SCSG
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 25 Peer Coaches recruited from local church 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PA conducted 8 PC training modules ➤ Hosted @ local immigration assistance center 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ PA recruited 5 smokers with flyers over 6 weeks from local church, hospital, & clinics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Smokers attended SCSG conducted by PC over 8 weeks ➤ SCSG at local church ➤ 5 smokers attended

Data Collection

- PC & participant demographic data
- PC ability to lead SCSG during 2 mock support groups with an evaluation checklist
- Focus group = PC experience
- Pre/Post Perceived social support with social support scale (MPSS)
- # cigarettes smoked Pre/Post SCSG
- Readiness Ruler to assess participant's readiness for change

Module	Peer Coach Training Topics
1	Harms of cigarette smoking/Nicotine Addiction & Withdrawal/Relapse
2	Relapse/Recognizing Triggers/Breaking Habit Links/Coping Mechanisms for Stress
3	Taking Smoking History/Medication Management/Community Referrals
4	Stages of Change/Assessing Readiness for Change/Motivational Interviewing Techniques
5	Assessing Social Support/How to Increase Social Support
6	Support Group Training/Text Messaging
7	Mock Support Group
8	Mock Support Group

Results

Peer Coaches

- 5 Hispanic, 1 Native American, 3 male, 3 female, & 5 bilingual
- 2 former smokers & 1 never smoker
- All 6 demonstrated ability to lead a SCSG by the end of 8-week training

Participants

- 5 attended
- 2 decreased daily quantity of cigarettes smoked
- 1 decreased A1C by 4 points
- 90% reported increased perceived social support

Unforeseen Challenges

- Peer coach attrition (25 start, 6 finish)
- Bible study started at church same week as SCSG
- Limited time to recruit smokers
- Participants attaining smoking cessation medications
- In-person SCSG switched to telephone support after 4 weeks due to global pandemic
- Telephone support received poor participant response

Implications for Practice

- Future efforts might consider financial incentives for PC
- Community recognition of program needed & should be done early in development of program since takes time to build trust
- PC trained over 8 weeks can effectively conduct SCSG to help decrease cigarettes quit
- Increased social support amongst smokers by PC can improve outcome of smokers other co-morbidities